

Carnitine Shuttle System Disruption by Ischemic Stroke

Abstract

In order to develop alternative treatments, it is necessary to acquire a comprehensive comprehension of the molecular mechanisms that underlie ischemic stroke. Ischemic stroke is known to cause a cell energy unevenness when glucose supply is denied, improving the job for energy creation through β -oxidation where acylcarnitines are fundamental for the transportation of unsaturated fats into the mitochondria. Albeit customary mass examination techniques empower touchy recognition of acylcarnitines, they don't give data on their overflows in different tissue areas. Quantitative mass spectrometry imaging, on the other hand, makes it simple to obtain objectively the concentrations and spatial distributions of endogenous molecules that have been detected. To investigate the distributions of acylcarnitines in stroke-affected mouse brain, we employ PA nano-DESI MSI, or pneumatically assisted nanospray desorption electrospray ionization mass spectrometry imaging. The inside principles empower quantitative imaging and explanation of endogenous acylcarnitines is accomplished by concentrating on discontinuity designs. Long-chain acylcarnitines significantly increased in the brain tissue of the middle cerebral artery occlusion (MCAO) stroke model as a result of ischemia, as shown by our findings. In addition, we estimate the activities of carnitine transporting enzymes and demonstrate malfunctions in the mitochondrial β -oxidation-affecting carnitine shuttle system. Based on our findings, it is clear that quantitative monitoring of metabolite distributions in distinct tissue regions is essential for comprehending cell compensation mechanisms for coping with stroke damage.

Keywords: Ischemic stroke • Acylcarnitines • Spectrometry imaging • Cerebral artery occlusion • Nanospray desorption • Quantitative Mass spectrometry

Introduction

Over 80% of all stroke cases are ischemic, making it one of the leading causes of death worldwide. Middle Cerebral Artery Occlusion (MCAO), in which an intraluminal suture physically blocks blood flow to a part of the brain, is the most common mouse model used to study ischemic stroke. Inflammation, oxidative stress, ionic imbalance, excitotoxicity, and apoptosis all occur as a result of the blood flow obstruction that is characteristic of stroke. These effects have a negative impact on the homeostasis of cells and are followed by apoptosis. The release of high intracellular levels of adenosine diphosphate (ADP), Ca^{2+} , and Na^{+} causes oxidative stress that damages the mitochondria. Ischemic stroke has a significant impact on mitochondria, the cells' primary energy production units [1].

The mitochondria can create energy through the oxidation of unsaturated fats (FAs), which is an elective when the fundamental supplements, like glucose, are not accessible to the synapses. Nonetheless, β -oxidation, the method involved with oxidizing FAs to deliver acetyl-CoA, isn't so positive as glucose oxidation since it requires 15% more oxygen, produces superoxides, and creates less ATP. However, FA oxidation in the brain can provide up to 20% of the required energy.

The transport of long-chain FAs (C14-C20) into the mitochondria is necessary for the multistep oxidation process. In particular, they are imported through the carnitine transport framework while the more limited chain (C3-C12) FAs basically diffuse through the mitochondrial layer. The FAs are coupled with carnitine via the enzyme

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carnitine palmitoyltransferase 1 (CPT1) and transported through the outer mitochondrial membrane once they are activated and in the form of acyl-CoA esters. Following that, the carnitine-acylcarnitine translocase (CACT) is used to move the acylcarnitines (ACs) across the inner mitochondrial membrane. Lastly, carnitine palmitoyltransferase 2 (CPT2) is responsible for the decoupling of the carnitine moiety from the acylcarnitines, resulting in the production of fatty acyl-CoA, which can enter the cycle of β -oxidation for the generation of energy. Numerous studies have evaluated the activity of CPT1 and CPT2 in biological systems using the concentrations of individual acylcarnitines or their ratios to carnitine [2].

The energy status of organic frameworks checked through examination of carnitine and ACs is ordinarily performed by coupling Fluid Chromatography (LC) to Mass Spectrometry (MS). The necessary sample homogenization makes it impossible to determine the distribution of analytes within specific parts or regions of the tissue, despite the fact that these methods are extremely robust and sensitive. Mass Spectrometry Imaging (MSI) techniques, which can provide localized information on ACs and thus directly assess the energy status of the cells in intact tissue sections, are therefore an appealing alternative. Nanospray desorption electrospray ionization (nano-DESI) is a MSI procedure that utilizes a limited fluid extraction of analytes from the tissue surface. To put it succinctly, the analytes are removed from the tissue and transformed into a liquid bridge that flows between two fused silica capillaries in front of the mass spectrometer. Following, the desorbed analytes are shipped through the second merged hairlike towards the bay of the mass spectrometer and ionized by electrospray or pneumatically helped (Dad) electrospray because of vacuum inside the MS or the Venturi impact, separately. By moving the example under the fluid scaffold, information is consistently gained for ensuing development of 2-D guides showing analyte circulations in the tissue. Through the data acquisition, the intensity of a specific ion from each scan event is represented by each pixel on the constructed 2-D maps. Quantitation is made possible in nano-DESI by adding standards to the solvent, and reactive reagents can be used to target

difficult analytes [3].

Here, we have utilized Dad nano-DESI MSI to concentrate on the energy status of the harmed cell area in ischemic stroke by planning the circulation of ACs in the MCAO stroke model. The circulations and comments of endogenous ACs were affirmed utilizing deuterated principles and discontinuity designs. In conclusion, we demonstrate that, in comparison to the healthy brain hemisphere, the brain hemisphere damaged by ischemic stroke had significantly more activity of CPT1 and CPT2. Overall, our findings point to impaired FA transport through the carnitine shuttle system as a result of ischemia [4,5].

Discussion

The onset of an ischemic stroke prevents oxygen and glucose, two essential nutrients, from reaching the ischemic region, resulting in cell damage and the need for alternative energy sources. The utilization of inner guidelines and explanation with MS/MS in blend with MSI empowers the synchronous evaluation of ischemic stroke on thirteen distinguished AC species. Long-chain ACs (C12-C20) is necessary for the introduction of activated long-chain FAs into the mitochondria during oxidative energy generation. This study's detection of C14-, C16-, C18-, and C18:1- and C18:2-AC accumulation is a well-known sign that FAs' transportation and oxidation have been disrupted. This suggests that metabolic dysfunctions in the carnitine shuttle system caused by an ischemic stroke restrict the utilization of long-chain FAs for the production of energy and, ultimately, cell survival. Short-chain FA metabolism is also disrupted, as evidenced by the accumulation of C4-AC in the ischemic area. Short-chain acyl-CoA dehydrogenase inhibition or defects have been linked to the accumulation of short-chain C4-carnitine in hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy, which has previously been linked to mitochondrial failure [6,7].

Using the ratio of acylcarnitines to free carnitine or acetylcarnitine, we measured enzymatic activity and found that CPT1 and CPT2 were more active in the ischemic tissue with no change in β -oxidation. This plainly shows that the carnitine transport framework is disturbed; despite the fact

that it is impossible to identify the point of disruption. For the most part, it would be sensible to expect that expanded measures of long-chain acylcarnitines is a result of expanded CPT1 activity and a diminished CPT2 action. In any case, this isn't upheld by our information. However, it is impossible to rule out the possibility that the overall effect we observe is the result of elevated CPT2 activity in addition to elevated CPT1 activity. In the carnitine shuttle system, CPT1 is the rate-limiting enzyme, so its increased activity may be justified by the absence of its natural inhibitor; malonyl-CoA. Malonyl-CoA is primarily produced by the metabolism of glucose; however, given the evidence of a decreased glucose level in the ischemic region, it is reasonable to anticipate that malonyl-CoA levels will also decrease. Long-chain acylcarnitines would therefore be found to be accumulating when CPT1 inhibition was limited [8,9]. Besides, an expanded action of CPT1 can prompt overabundance change of the long-chain FAs 18:1 and 18:2 to the relating acylcarnitines, which would make sense of the absence of FA 18:1 and 18:2 amassing in our information. It would be interesting for future research to keep an eye on the enzymatic activities of the carnitine-shuttle system during ischemia to learn more about the main step that causes the disruption and the contributions made by the isoforms that have already been identified. Acquiring a more profound comprehension of the sub-atomic instruments enacted during stroke will enormously add to future focusing of chemicals for treatment and harm mitigation [9,10].

Conclusion

It is notable that stroke is an inconvenient condition for cell endurance. By imaging with Dad nano-DESI MSI we show that C4-AC and long-chain ACs aggregate in the ischemic locale of the cerebrum after MCAO. By measuring thirteen carnitine species, we gauge the enzymatic movement of the carnitine shipping proteins CPT1 and CPT2 by working out carnitine proportions. In spite of our finding that both CPT1 and CPT2 are expanded in the ischemic locale, we estimate

that the movement of CPT1 is more raised because of the absence of its normal inhibitor malonyl-CoA that is generally shaped through usually utilized energy producing pathways. The unique distributions and abundances of long-chain ACs in ischemic stroke brain tissue are revealed for the first time, and overall, our findings are consistent with existing bulk analysis theories.

References

1. Feigin VL, Brainin M, Norrving B *et al.* World Stroke Organization (WSO): Global Stroke Fact Sheet 2022. *Int J Stroke.* 17, 18-29 (2022).
2. Sommer CJ. Ischemic Stroke: Experimental Models and Reality. *Acta Neuropathol.* 133, 245-261 (2017).
3. Doyle KP, Simon RP, Stenzel Poore MP. Mechanisms of Ischemic Brain Damage. *Neuropharmacology.* 55, 310-318 (2008).
4. Ebert D, Haller RG, Walton ME. Energy Contribution of Octanoate to Intact Rat Brain Metabolism Measured by ¹³C Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy. *J Neurosci.* 23, 5928-5935 (2003).
5. Schönfeld P, Wojtczak L. Short- and Medium-Chain Fatty Acids in Energy Metabolism: The Cellular Perspective. *J Lipid Res.* 57, 943-954 (2016).
6. Reuter SE, Evans AM. Carnitine and Acylcarnitines: Pharmacokinetic, Pharmacological and Clinical Aspects. *Clin Pharmacokinet.* 51, 553-572 (2012).
7. Wu, T, Zheng X, Yang M *et al.* Serum Lipid Alterations Identified in Chronic Hepatitis B, Hepatitis B Virus-Associated Cirrhosis and Carcinoma Patients. *Sci Rep.* 7, 42710 (2017).
8. Saiki S, Hatano T, Fujimaki *et al.* Decreased Long-Chain Acylcarnitines from Insufficient β -Oxidation as Potential Early Diagnostic Markers for Parkinson's Disease. *Sci Rep.* 7, 7328 (2017).
9. Neumann EK, Djambazova KV, CMayoli RM *et al.* Multimodal Imaging Mass Spectrometry: Next Generation Molecular Mapping in Biology and Medicine. *J Am Soc Mass Spectrom.* 31, 2401-2415 (2020).
10. Laskin J, Heath BS, Roach PJ *et al.* Tissue Imaging Using Nanospray Desorption Electrospray Ionization Mass Spectrometry. *Anal Chem.* 46, 141-148 (2012).